

101132933 – AD-RIDDLE

Real-World Implementation, Deployment and Validation of Early Detection Tools and Lifestyle Enhancement

WP7 – Ethics, health economics and health technology assessment

D7.1 Review on the ethics of dementia risk: A scoping review of ethical reflection and concerns about population level health screening approaches for AD/dementia risk for cognitively healthy and at-risk populations

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DEFINITIONS

Participants of the AD-RIDDLE Consortium are referred to herein according to the following codes:

RS: Region Stockholm, Karolinska Universitetssjukhuset – Sweden (**The Coordinator**)
KI: Karolinska Institutet, Department of Neurobiology, Care Sciences and Society – Sweden
FBHI: Stiftelsen Fingers Brain Health Institute – Sweden
UGOT: Goeteborgs Universitet – Sweden
ULUND: Lunds Universitet – Sweden
UEF: Itä-Suomen Yliopisto, University of Eastern Finland – Finland
AUMC: Stichting Amsterdam UMC – The Netherlands
UM: Universiteit Maastricht – The Netherlands
BBRC: Fundació Barcelonaβeta Brain Research Center – Spain
SYNAPSE: Synapse Research Management Partners S.L – Spain
AE: Alzheimer Europe – Luxembourg
ADI: Alzheimer’s Disease International – United States
UNIPG: Università Degli Studi di Perugia – Italy
GV: Gates Ventures LLC – United States (**The Co-Coordinator**)
COMBINOSTICS: Combinostics Oy – Finland
Fujirebio: Fujirebio Europe NV – Belgium
SARD: Sanofi-Aventis Recherche & Development – France
C2N: C2N Diagnostics LLC – United States
neotiv GmbH: Neotiv GmbH – Germany
CCL: Cambridge Cognition Limited – United Kingdom
DAVOS: Davos Alzheimer’s Collaborative – United States
VGR: VÄSTRA GÖTALANDSREGIONEN – Sweden
ULEIC: University of Leicester – United Kingdom
ICL: Imperial College of Science, Technology and medicine – United Kingdom
NICE: National Institute for Health and Care Excellence – United Kingdom
SUS: SANOFI US Services Inc – United States
SADG: SANOFI-AVENTIS Deutschland GMBH – Germany

Grant agreement	The agreement signed between the beneficiaries and the IHI for the undertaking of the AD-RIDDLE project (101132933).
Project	The sum of all activities carried out in the framework of the Grant Agreement.
Consortium	The AD-RIDDLE Consortium, comprising the above-mentioned legal entities.
Consortium agreement	Agreement concluded amongst AD-RIDDLE participants for the implementation of the Grant Agreement. Such an agreement shall not affect the parties’ obligations to the Community and/or to one another arising from the Grant Agreement.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The AD-RIDDLE project aims to transform the detection, diagnosis, prevention and treatment of Alzheimer's disease (AD) across healthcare settings. To achieve this, a multi-modal toolbox platform will be developed, which includes community outreach tools, a combination of biomarkers and digital cognitive tools and validated algorithms. The platform's algorithms will identify people who might benefit from preventive interventions or drug therapies, using a precision medicine approach.

To ensure the quality of the AD-RIDDLE platform and to provide ethical guidance on potential socio-ethical implications of the project, a review of relevant literature was conducted. Scoping reviews, sometimes referred to as mapping reviews, have been likened to 'reconnaissance' work aimed at clarifying working definitions and conceptual boundaries of a given topic or field, covering both quantitative and qualitative research.

Given the fairly broad scope of this project, and the complex and heterogeneous nature of ethical issues, it was decided to conduct a systematic scoping review in accordance with guidance developed by the JBI to standardise the conduct and reporting of the scoping reviews. The review set out to explore the ethical concerns linked to the development and implementation of population-level health screening approaches for AD/dementia risk (meeting core ethical principles of beneficence, non-maleficence, justice and autonomy, psychological and social issues), potentially with a focus on health equity in risk-reduction programmes and the communication of dementia risk at population level or to asymptomatic individuals.

The scoping review will feed into ongoing Public Involvement work with people who have cognitive problems, people with dementia, carers, older people and people considered at risk or with an interest in brain health to ensure that this research reflects their needs, concerns, hopes and priorities. In combination with the Public Involvement work and a policy and practice review, the review will inform the development of guidance and recommendations designed to inform the AD-RIDDLE platform design, feasibility testing and development, and promote further reflection on the socio-ethical implications of the project, all of which will facilitate the real-world implementation of the AD-RIDDLE project.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Alzheimer’s disease (AD), the most common cause of dementia, is a significant global health challenge affecting over 55 million people worldwide, with predictions of further increase (ADI 2024). In this context, the possibility of addressing underlying causes and risk factors for dementia before the onset of clinical symptoms is a promising endeavour. It is estimated that 67 million people are at risk of AD dementia (i.e. have “preclinical” or prodromal AD) in Europe alone (Dumas et al. 2023). Recent advances in disease-modifying therapies and preventive multidomain interventions addressing lifestyle and vascular factors offer new opportunities for research and intervention in the early stages of dementia (van Dyck et al. 2023). Screening for dementia risk can therefore potentially contribute towards efforts to predict and eventually prevent dementia at population level.

Aligned with these important shifts in therapeutic approaches to dementia, the AD-RIDDLE project aims to create a real-world implementation, deployment and validation of early detection tools and lifestyle enhancement. It aims to increase the timeliness and accuracy of early detection of risk and the diagnosis of Alzheimer’s disease, as well as develop therapeutic solutions to reduce the risk of developing dementia. This requires the identification of people who could potentially benefit from preventive interventions or drug therapies within the population.

The scoping review presented in this report will inform the development and implementation of such tools. The review set out to explore the ethical issues related to the development and implementation of health screening approaches for AD/dementia risk at population level. It was designed to reflect core ethical principles of beneficence, non-maleficence, justice and autonomy, psychological and social issues, and specifically highlight any issues related to health equity in risk-reduction programmes and the communication of dementia risk at population level or to asymptomatic individuals.

This scoping review raised a few conceptual challenges. The first of these conceptual challenges concerned the definition of dementia *screening* in the scientific literature. Screening should not be mistaken for *ad hoc* testing for dementia or for diagnosis of conditions. With few exceptions, screening tests do not aim to diagnose conditions but rather to identify people who test positive who then require further evaluation with diagnostic tests or procedures (Givler and Givler 2017). According to the United Kingdom National Screening Committee, screening implies a population level approach, and not individual sporadic testing. It primarily targets asymptomatic individuals to determine the likelihood (or risk) of developing a condition, such as dementia. This is also reflected in the WHO definition of screening as consisting of “the use of simple tests across an apparently healthy population in order to identify individuals who have risk factors or early stages of disease, but do not yet have symptoms” (Wilson et al, 1968). The emphasis is therefore on simple approaches to the identification of people who do not yet have a particular medical condition but who are at risk of developing it OR who are in the very early, asymptomatic stage of a condition. The term “early disease detection” is sometimes used to refer to “all forms of early detection whether by screening, physical examination or other means” (Wilson and Jungner, 1968). This can lead to some confusion as this could include mass (population) screening, selective screening and case-finding.

The second conceptual challenge is related to the rationale or purpose of the screening. Population-level screening is not conducted out of mere curiosity but rather because the early detection of risk factors or early disease is beneficial for a clinical or public health outcome. For example, it has been

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suggested that health screening can only be applied to presumably healthy (asymptomatic) populations, not individuals. It has been further suggested that acceptable and reasonably accurate tests should be used, for diseases that are treatable and for which outcomes when treated early are better, compared to people whose conditions are not detected, and for which the harm and costs associated with screening do not outweigh the benefits (Speechley, Kunnilathu, Aluckal, Balakrishna, Mathew and George 2017; Steele 2018). The purpose of screening for inclusion in dementia research is quite specific. It differs to screening for health reasons (e.g. used for the purpose of recruitment and to stratify people into different sub-groups). Screening for risk in connection with participation in research is therefore beyond the scope of this review because the purpose is different and it cannot be assumed that the ethical implications of such screening would be the same.

A widely-cited set of criteria developed by Wilson and Jungner (1968), which was framed in the context of “early disease detection” (as mentioned earlier, not limited solely to screening for risk, including case finding), emphasises the nature of the condition to be “screened” and of the tests available, as well as the existence of facilities to diagnose and treat the condition (please see below).

1. “The condition sought should be an important health problem.
2. There should be an accepted treatment for patients with recognised disease.
3. Facilities for diagnosis and treatment should be available.
4. There should be a recognisable latent or early symptomatic stage.
5. There should be a suitable test or examination.
6. The test should be acceptable to the population.
7. The natural history of the condition, including development from latent to declared disease, should be adequately understood.
8. There should be an agreed policy on whom to treat as patients.
9. The cost of case-finding (including diagnosis and treatment of patients diagnosed) should be economically balanced in relation to possible expenditure on medical care as a whole.
10. Case-finding should be a continuing process and not a 'once and for all' project.”

(Wilson and Jungner, 1968, p.26-27)

The third criterion above is relevant to screening for AD/dementia risk because symptomatic and/or disease modifying treatment is not yet/widely available but this may change in the near future.

The third conceptual challenge concerns the definition of *risk* of developing dementia. Current research indicates the following risk categories for dementia: genetic, lifestyle-related, social and behavioural risk factors, health-related risk factors such as NCDs and injuries (Livingston et al. 2024), biomarker changes (Lu et al. 2024), cognitive decline such as Mild Cognitive Impairment, and ageing (Campbell et al. 2013). Challenges emerge when researchers speak of screening for so-called pre-clinical or prodromal Alzheimer’s disease rather than for risk. Indeed, a so-called preclinical, asymptomatic phase or prodromal phase of Alzheimer’s disease will not necessarily evolve into a clinically significant onset of dementia (Vos et al. 2015). Moreover, the conceptualisation of Alzheimer’s disease as a pathological process along a continuum reflects an increasing health trend whereby health and disease are no longer simply two discrete, mutually exclusive states. Rather, health is “a matter of graduation, probabilities and risk factors that need to be identified, calculated and controlled” (Karlavish 2011). For a discussion about ethical issues linked to the identification of risk in relation to the conceptualisation of Alzheimer’s disease along a continuum, please see Alzheimer Europe’s report on

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that topic (2016). For the purpose of this review, we conceive the existence of preconditions and biomarkers eventually leading to dementia as a risk factor rather than as the actual diagnosis of a pre-clinical stage of dementia. Ethical issues related to the disclosure of a “pre-dementia” condition are not necessarily the same as those found in the disclosure of “risk factors”. This is because the former is presented in the context of a diagnostic workup, perhaps resulting from subjective awareness of cognitive deterioration, and the latter in the context of a possible future condition that may or may not actually occur at an unspecified time.

2. METHODS

2.1. Research questions/objectives

The review set out to summarise ethical reflection and concerns in the literature in relation to screening and risk reduction programmes for AD/dementia risk. More specifically, it aims to answer the following research question:

What are the ethical issues (risks, benefits and challenges) linked to the development and implementation of population-based health screening [approaches] for AD/dementia risk?

2.2 Choice of review type and definition of evidence

It was decided to conduct a scoping review of literature in order to provide an answer to the above-mentioned research question. Scoping reviews are suitable for the identification and mapping of relevant evidence, ideas or concepts related to a specific, pre-determined topic, context, concept or issue. Scoping reviews are particularly useful, for example, where evidence is emerging and not yet amenable to questions of effectiveness. This is the case for the topic of this review which is about a concept that is not yet commonplace and has not yet been implemented at population level in Europe. Scoping reviews are appropriate when complex questions are being asked about interventions which cannot be meaningfully compared or evaluated (Peters et al. 2015b).

Scoping reviews are somewhat broader than traditional systematic reviews. They can include multiple types of evidence (including grey literature, policy documents and online media) and cover different methodologies. They do not involve a qualitative or quantitative synthesis of data but, rather, a comprehensive overview of evidence. As such reviews are not designed to underpin clinical decision making and do not require an assessment of methodological quality or risk of bias (Levac, Colquhoun & O’Brien 2010; Peters et al. 2010; Peters et al. 2015b; Brady De La Rosa, Nair & Leischow 2019; Truman & Elliott 2019; Peters et al. 2020). Scoping reviews can be iterative and flexible, provided that they are conducted in a systematic manner. Any deviations from the protocol must be reported in a transparent manner, as well as any necessary adjustments to questions, the search and/or inclusion/exclusion criteria (Levac, Colquhoun & O’Brien 2010; Peters et al. 2020). They typically present and describe relevant characteristics of the included sources of evidence. This raises the question as to what counts as evidence in relation to ethical concepts, ideas and reflection.

Angehrn et al. (2020) suggest that when attempting to characterise salient ethical arguments, the focus should be on the claims being made and the arguments supporting them, not on how often a given claim appears in the literature as frequency is not considered important. As to what constitutes an ethical issue,

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we adopted an approach based on a very broad understanding of ethical principles, concepts and theories. This includes, for example, the four core principles of the principlist biomedical ethics approach developed by Beauchamp & Childress (2009) and an understanding of various theories and approaches which had been considered in Alzheimer Europe’s various ethics working groups between 2012 and 2019 in relation to various topics of relevance to the lives and wellbeing of people with dementia and their carers/supporters (e.g. disability, ethical dilemmas, the use of assistive technology, legal capacity, supported decision making, intercultural care and support, and sex, gender and sexuality). This included other principles and values which are perhaps equally important in various different contexts (e.g. in everyday interactions with other people, in relationships with friends and family, in social care and in residential care settings) such as trustworthiness, honesty, integrity, compassion, well-being, confidentiality and respect for privacy, personhood and dignity. Our approach was broad and not limited to a single approach/philosophy (e.g. utilitarian, consequentialist, fairness, common good, human rights, deontological or virtue).

This therefore represented a combined top-down and bottom-up approach whereby the reviewers had an awareness of certain ethical concepts that might arise in the literature but also an openness to the possibility of newly identified ethical and social issues, which could be described and the possible connections and interdependencies identified, and considered in the light of the AD-RIDDLE project.

2.3 Population of interest and type of screening

The population of interest for this scoping review was members of the general public who do not have dementia. This could include people believed to be cognitively healthy, as well as people with subjective cognitive decline, people with MCI, people considered at risk of dementia and people classed as asymptomatic/at risk of AD, but not people with dementia. The risk status applies to any form of dementia, not just AD dementia.

With regard to the different types of screening for dementia risk, our focus was on screening within the framework of primary and secondary prevention as proposed by Shürman and Trachsel (2023). Within this framework, primary dementia prevention would cover screening and intervention in asymptomatic individuals, groups or populations. Secondary dementia screening would cover screening and preventive intervention in people with early clinical signs of AD (e.g. at the prodromal stage of AD, prior to AD dementia) of large proportions of the population such as older people. These approaches should ideally reduce the incidence rates of AD dementia (Schürmann and Trachsel 2023). This classification still takes into consideration classical distinctions between primary and secondary prevention.

With regard to the target groups of screening and prevention measures, this would fall into the category of population-based or “universal” prevention which targets entire populations or large subpopulations such as older adults (Schürmann and Trachsel, 2023).

2.4 Inclusion and exclusion criteria

It was agreed that articles fulfilling the following criteria should be included in the review.

- Publication in peer-reviewed journal
- English language
- Study designs: original quantitative (cross sectional, longitudinal, surveys, interventions etc.), qualitative (interviews, focus groups, text or audio analysis and any approaches using qualitative research methods), mixed methods and opinion pieces

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- Outcomes: screening approaches for AD/dementia risk; health equity in risk-reduction programmes for AD/dementia and communication of dementia risk at population level or to asymptomatic individuals

It was decided that dissertations, book chapters and conference proceedings should be excluded. No restriction of date was set. In keeping with the nature of scoping reviews (as opposed to systematic reviews), a formal assessment of the methodological quality of the included studies was not conducted.

2.5 Databases, key terms and search strings

The following databases were searched for relevant articles:

1. PubMed
2. PsycINFO
3. CINAHL
4. Web of Science
5. Phil Papers

The following key terms and search strings were applied to the different databases:

1. PubMed (("ethic*" OR "moral*" OR "health equity" OR "digital equity") AND ("screening" OR "detection" OR "risk reduction" OR prevention) AND ("dementia" OR "MCI" OR "AD" OR Alzheimer* OR cognit*))
2. PsycInfo TX ("ethic*" OR "moral*" OR "health equity" OR "digital equity") AND TX ("screening" OR "detection" OR "risk reduction" OR prevention) AND ("dementia" OR "MCI" OR "AD" OR Alzheimer* OR cognit*)
3. CINAHL TX ("ethic*" OR "moral*" OR "health equity" OR "digital equity") AND TX ("screening" OR "detection" OR "risk reduction" OR "prevention") AND TX ("dementia" OR "MCI" OR "AD" OR Alzheimer* OR cognit*)
4. Web of Science (("ethic*" OR "moral*" OR "health equity" OR "digital equity") AND ("screening" OR "detection" OR "risk reduction" OR prevention) AND ("dementia" OR "MCI" OR "AD" OR Alzheimer* OR cognit*))
5. PhilPapers (ethics OR moral OR health equity AND screening OR risk reduction AND Alzheimer OR dementia OR MCI OR cognition)

Software

The Covidence software platform was used to manage the search results from the five different databases and for coordination among five reviewers. The Covidence platform facilitated the review process through importing citations, removing duplicates, coordinating the number of reviewers, recording trail of reviewer decisions, decision choices (yes, no or maybe), assigning conflict resolution when reviewers disagreed, and title and abstract inclusion/exclusion criteria and key words. A yes or maybe decision resulted in a full text article review.

Expanded literature search

In the light of the small number of articles retained in the review and to increase the likelihood of detecting very recent articles, the following additional searches were conducted:

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1. A standard Google search (conducted by PP) for possible further grey or academic literature:
 - with the search string “ethics screening risk alzheimer” (including synonyms) from 2020 to 2024. This resulted in 72,200 results with no additional articles fulfilling the scoping review criteria being identified in the first 10 pages of results.
 - with the search string “screening AND risk AND Alzheimer AND ethical” from 2020 to 2024. This resulted in 68,500 results with no additional articles fulfilling the scoping review criteria in the first 10 pages of results.
2. An additional Google scholar search (conducted by DG) with the search string “screening AND risk AND (Alzheimer OR Alzheimer's OR dementia) AND (ethics OR ethical OR moral” between 2020 and 2024. This resulted in 29,700 results with one additional article being detected in the first 200 results.

In the above searches, the title and abstract of the first 10 pages or 200 results were screened (for ethical issues linked to population-based screening) and, where necessary, the full article was obtained for further clarification.

Relevant publicly accessible deliverables from EU-funded projects were consulted (e.g. AI-MIND, MOPEAD, ROADMAP, RADAR-AD etc.) but did not result in any additional articles.

2.6 Review/selection process – review process

In view of the large number of articles extracted in the initial search and after the automatic removal of duplicates, a first selection was made on the basis of the titles (by DG, RS and PP). In most cases, it could be clearly ascertained from the title which articles were totally inappropriate (e.g. wrong topic). In case of doubt, reviewers looked at the abstract and if still in doubt, the article was retained.

As a second step, the abstracts of the remaining articles were reviewed by 5 reviewers (DG, RS, PP, AD and SC), with each abstract being reviewed by two people. Because of certain linguistic and conceptual challenges (please see “Limitations” section of this report), we set up a review team of 5 (eventually 6) researchers, arranged for each abstract and selected full articles to be reviewed by 2 people and had frequent discussions about what should and should not be included or excluded, as well as group discussions to come to an agreement about certain articles.

In keeping with the philosophy and structure of Covidence, it was not possible to allocate specific articles to specific people. Each person randomly reviewed an equal number of articles and as soon as an article had been reviewed by two people it was either rejected or retained in the system. Where there was disagreement between reviewers, each article was discussed in an online meeting with all the reviewers. The two reviewers of each article read through the abstract again, reflected on their decision and the reasons for it and the other members of the review team gave feedback in an open discussion. The two initial reviewers then agreed whether to include or exclude each of the articles for which there had been no clear decision. This approach worked well and it was not necessary to elect a third person to decide on the issue.

The third stage involved a full review of the selected articles by 6 members of the review team (i.e. one additional person joined the team), again with each article being reviewed by 2 people and a review team process to deal with any disagreement about inclusion/exclusion. It was agreed that should one

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of the reviewers be an author or co-author of any article, s/he would not review that particular article. For this third stage of the review, it was decided, for pragmatic reasons, to switch from Covidence to a tabular formula. The review team felt that this was manageable for the articles retained for full review and would allow for greater flexibility and clarity in the charting of the emerging ideas and ethical reflection covered in the articles finally selected. The spreadsheet was tested on the first five articles and slightly adjusted to ensure that the information recorded was meaningful and to avoid spending too much time recording details of articles that would be subsequently rejected.

In a recent systematic literature review, Angehrn et al. (2020) reflected on a potential bias stemming from “some ethical arguments being missed or misinterpreted when different reviewers appraise manuscripts and documents in a different manner”. We aimed to avoid this bias by means of regular meetings to discuss progress with the review and any uncertainties (e.g. regarding the scope and purpose of the review, as well as individual articles). It was also beneficial to have reviewers from different backgrounds, namely, psychology, sociology, anthropology, nursing home management, biomedicine and policy.

2.7 Analysis, charting and reporting of the results

The goal when charting the results of a scoping review is to provide a logical and descriptive summary of the results that align to the objectives and questions of the review (Peters et al. 2015). The goal of this scoping review was to explore literature on ethical issues (risks, benefits and challenges) linked to the development and implementation of population-based health screening [approaches] for AD/dementia risk. There was initially also a secondary aim which was to focus on ethical issues related to health inequity and the communication of risk to asymptomatic people (in the context of the broader research question). We considered that literature on these sub-topics would emerge from the search because they are covered by the overall search terms for ethical issues. For health equity, we nevertheless added that term to the search strings. The charting spreadsheet was used to record key characteristics and information of relevance to the overall goal and to the research questions in the articles included in the final full review.

Data extraction and analysis was carried out by means of a bottom-up approach conducted by 5 members of the review team (DG, RS, PP, AD and SL), guided by the research question, highlighting relevant issues addressed according to a broad guiding framework. This was not limited to the largely principlist approach described in the Description of Activities. It also covered issues which might be considered as having a more virtue ethics, care ethics or rights-based ethics focus (e.g. bearing in mind issues related to personhood, relationships, dependency, trustworthiness and stigma). For each article, one member of the review team added the relevant information to the spreadsheet and this included a summary of any ethical issues addressed.

It should be noted that the vast majority of articles addressing ethical issues related to population-based screening are not based on studies involving participants. Therefore, the charting of the articles is somewhat different to many other scoping reviews. When charting the content and issues addressed in the final articles, and in keeping with the broad and more focused interest in potential ethical issues, we created three columns for a short overview of relevant content, namely:

- ethical issues linked to population-based health screening for AD/dementia risk,

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- issues related to health inequity and
- the communication of risk in that context.

In addition, we recorded any information provided related to gender, ethnicity, level of education, socio-economic status and geographical location within the context of the ethical reflection on the above issues.

The results, concepts and different perspectives were organised into categories and overriding themes, and summarised in a narrative description (see Results section below) and their relevance to the AD-RIDDLE project discussed. Thematic analysis is a widely used approach in qualitative research. It typically describes a process to identify, analyse and report repeated patterns of information or meaning within the data that is relevant to the research question. Research data, in turn, can be considered as “any information collected, observed, or generated during a research project to answer specific questions or test hypotheses” (Hassan 2024). The ethical issues identified in this scoping review were mainly derived from personal or group reflection amongst researchers and ethicists, rather than from research participants. The ethical issues identified in the review were organised into broad categories and overriding themes (e.g. as described by Braun & Clarke 2006 and Vaismoradi Turunen & Bondas 2013).

A draft of the deliverable was circulated for internal review prior to submission (which had been extended from December 2024 to June 2025).

3. RESULTS

3.1. Overview of articles screened

A total of 8,953 articles were retrieved from the databases searched and an additional 437 from additional searches on Google Scholar and from citations. After removal of duplicates, 7,552 titles were screened. This led to the exclusion of 7,116 articles and the subsequent retrieval of 236 articles. After exclusion of 178 articles, 58 full articles were reviewed and this led to the retention of 6 articles for final inclusion.

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3.1. Articles included in the full review

1. Calza L, Beltramia D, Gagliardia G, Ghidonic E, Marcelloc N, Rossini-Favretti R, Tamburini F (2015). Should we screen for cognitive decline and dementia? *Maturitas* 82: 28–35
2. Gordon M (2013). Identification of Potential or Preclinical Cognitive Impairment and the Implications of Sophisticated Screening with Biomarkers and Cognitive Testing: Does It Really Matter? *BioMed Research International*, <https://doi.org/10.1155/2013/976130>
3. Horstkötter D, Deckers K & Köhler S (2021). Dementia Risk Reduction in Mid-Life: The Real Ethical Challenge, *A JOB Neuroscience*, 12(4): 250-253, DOI: 10.1080/21507740.2021.1941401
4. McKeever A & Agius M (2018). Dementia Risk Assessment And Risk Reduction Using Cardiovascular Risk Factors. *Psychiatria Danubina*, 18(30), Suppl. 7: 469-474
5. Schürmann J & Trachsel M (2023). Ethical Issues of Primary and Secondary Dementia Prevention: A Narrative Literature Review. *GeroPsych*. 36(4): 177–187
6. Weatherby TJM & Agius M (2018). Ethical And Organisational Considerations In Screening For Dementia. *Psychiatria Danubina*, 30(7): 463-468

3.2. Ethical issues addressed in the literature regarding population-based screening for risk of AD/dementia

Introduction

The following ethical issues emerged from the literature and were grouped into two broad themes, namely the impact on the individual and issues at the level of society. Table 1 below provides an overview of the various issues addressed in the literature, which are then described in more details below.

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Table 1: overview of key themes

Themes	Detail of ethical issues covered	References
Impact on the individual:		
Balancing potential benefit with the risk of harm: non-maleficence	Potential harm: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Emotional impact of being declared at risk without effective treatment for dementia Insurance eligibility/premiums issues Employment and healthcare discrimination Fear Concerns about decision-making capacity Being called into question Despair and hopelessness Catastrophic reaction to AD stigma Consequences of failure to ensure privacy and confidentiality Increased risk of suicide Overdiagnosis Interventions for people who are not truly at high risk of AD/dementia 	Gordon 2013; Calza et al. 2015, McKeever and Agius 2018; Weatherby and Agius 2018; Horstkötter et al. 2021; Schürmann and Trachsel 2023.
	...to consider in light of... <ul style="list-style-type: none"> moral <i>fault</i> of potentially reducing the risk of AD/dementia in cognitively healthy middle-aged people Engaging in low-risk interventions like encouraging healthy lifestyle modifications 	Deckers and Köhler 2021; McKeever and Agius 2018
Balancing potential benefit with the risk of harm: beneficence	Potential benefits of screening (for cognitive frailty or risk of AD/dementia) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Detection and correction of potentially reversible cognitive decline secondary to non-neurological disorders, malnutrition and inappropriate polytherapies. Appropriate management of hospitalisation, surgery and anaesthesia Appropriate safety measures to help prevent accidents Better adherence and management of other medical conditions (e.g. social isolation, depression) 	Gordon 2013; Calza et al. 2015; McKeever and Agius 2018; Horstkötter et al. 2021

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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enabling policy makers to take evidence-based decisions and predict and plan care needs and housing decisions • Empowerment (e.g. to take preventive measures) • Better planning for the future • Feeling in control over one’s future • Reassurance (if low risk declared) 	
Empowerment or missed opportunities	Empowerment potentially attached to early awareness of risk and its reduction	McKeever & Agius 2018; Horstkötter et al. 2021
	No guarantee that people at high risk will be willing or able to make lifestyle changes	Bosco et al. 2020; Bruinsma et al. 2023
	...or that the “worried well” will actually be reassured.	Gordon 2013
Autonomy and personal responsibility	Interest of knowing one’s risk while cognitive impairment is widespread among people aged 80+	Gordon 2023
	Issue of ‘individual responsabilisation’ following risk screening	Horstkötter et al. 2021
Blame and stigma	Potential blame and increased stigma for people who refuse screening and develop dementia later	Horstkötter, Deckers and Köhler 2021; Weatherby and Agius 2018, Schürmann and Trachsel 2023
	Shift to individual responsibility in making risk-reducing lifestyle choices leading to blame and stigma	Schürmann and Trachsel 2023
Long-term impact of risk timeframe on personal life/identity	Time lap between identification of risk and actual occurrence of AD/dementia	Gordon 2013; Horstkötter, Deckers and Köhler 2021
	Concern about medicalisation of normal health in absence of treatment or risk reduction strategies	McKeown, Mahli and Singh 2021
	Consideration for emotional and financial impact on people’s life	Gordon 2013
Issues at the level of society		
Target condition for screening	Interest in broadening the scope for risk screening beyond AD/dementia alone	Calza L, et al. 2015

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	Benefit of population-based cognitive screening versus hazard of potential Alzheimer’s disease overdiagnosis	Calza L, et al. 2015
Validity and bias in the applicability of screening tools	Limited nature of certain screening tools for the risk of AD/dementia	Calza et al. 2015
	Bias in the use of screening tools not yet validated on populations with diverse characteristics	Emanuel, Wendler and Grady 2000
	use of cognitive screening tests in the context of population-based screening versus more targeted approaches.	Calza et al. 2015
Trade-off between accuracy and usefulness/relevance	Distinction between screening for the benefit of society versus the individual	Calza et al. 2015, Gordon 2013
	Trade-off between degree of accuracy, cost and burden of different screening approaches	Schürmann and Trachsel 2023; Doroszkiewicz and Mroczko, 2022
	Implications of risk measurements for individuals with regard to their relatives, workplace and insurance.	Weatherby and Agius 2018
Relationship to research	Ethics of screening for research purposes as different from screening for health purposes	Calza L, et al. 2015
Economic considerations	Financial implications of dementia risk screening and effective regulatory checks	Gordon 2013
	Ethics of financial incentives for doctors in providing screening	Weatherby and Agius 2018
	Issue of spending scarce public resources on screening and prevention for AD/dementia without solid scientific evidence	Schürmann and Trachsel 2023; Horstkötter et al. 2021
Health inequity	Screening and prevention hampered by social injustice in educational and/or economic disadvantage	Weatherby and Agius 2018; Schürmann and Trachsel 2023

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Impact on the individual

Balancing potential benefit with the risk of harm

A key question in relation to benefit is whether the detection of people at high risk of cognitive impairment or dementia is ethically justifiable and to answer this question it is necessary to reflect also on the risk of harm.

“In keeping with the ethical principle of nonmaleficence, one would have to demonstrate a very positive countering ethical principle of beneficence in order to justify the wholesale introduction of screening tests or batteries of tests to make an early diagnosis of a definable clinical state affecting cognition which is likely to progress to a dementia-like condition” (Gordon 2013, p.4).

As ethics is about good and bad or right and wrong in relation to people and people’s lives, there may be some overlap between some of the issues addressed in this report (e.g. empowerment, stigma, discrimination etc.) and various ethical principles or concepts (such as beneficence and non-maleficence). Certain issues are therefore mentioned briefly below and addressed more fully in separate sub-sections.

The medico-ethical principle of non-maleficence means that healthcare professionals have a duty to do no harm and to prevent patients being harmed through neglect. This principle is usually considered alongside that of beneficence, which is another core principle in medical ethics that serves to ensure that healthcare professionals act in accordance with perceived best interests (or, in keeping with recent debates, with a person’s “known will and preferences” if available). This includes an active component (i.e. helping others to achieve what they consider as being good or promoting their wellbeing). A key concern is what the benefits and risks might be of screening processes that identify people with normal cognition, those who are potentially at risk and the so-called “worried well” as being at risk when beneficial interventions might not yet be in place (Gordon 2013). Examples of the “worried well” include relatives of people who have or have died with dementia, who Gordon suggests may wish “to decrease their own risk, at times in an understandably fearful or even excessive manner” (Gordon, 2013, p.2).

This is closely linked to the question of whether people who are asymptomatic should be told that they are more likely than others to develop a cognitive impairment (Calza et al. 2015). Whilst the benefit of finding out that one has a treatable condition is considered evident, the risk of disclosing an AD diagnosis in asymptomatic or minimally symptomatic persons with full insight, with no specific treatment options currently available plus the risk of catastrophic reactions related to an “AD-stigma”, has been questioned (Calza et al. 2015). This reflection is inextricably linked to how such risk is communicated but this was not addressed in depth in the articles included in this review, with experiences having been obtained mainly from controlled study settings (e.g. memory clinics, clinical trials etc.) (e.g. Visser et al. 2021). Calza et al. (2015) describe this as “disclosing an AD **diagnosis**” (i.e. as having AD, albeit in the pre-dementia phase), rather than as someone being informed that they are **at risk** or increased risk of cognitive decline or AD dementia.

There are different opinions about what can be considered as beneficial and how much risk and what level of harm can be considered acceptable. Gordon (2013) calls for “proper controlled studies to determine whether or not “early identification” with subsequent specific and beneficial or best-suited pharmacological interventions will bear tangible and measurable benefit, clinically, psychosocially,

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and economically". It should, however, be noted that most of the articles included in this review were published prior to the recent development of disease modifying drugs, when there was little to offer people identified as being at risk, other than life-style modifications and strategies to promote mental and social stimulation. If, in the near future, such drugs were to be successfully approved, marketed and made widely available, appraisals of potential risk and benefit may shift but there may also be other ethical issues to consider.

Non-maleficence

Several forms of harm are discussed in the literature such as:

- the emotional impact of being declared at risk for a condition for which there is, as yet, no effective treatment
- issues related to insurance eligibility/premiums for what could be construed as a “pre-existing” condition
- potential discrimination in the fields of employment and healthcare
- fear
- concerns about decision-making capacity being called into question
- despair and hopelessness
- catastrophic reaction to AD stigma
- consequences of failure to ensure privacy and confidentiality
- an increased risk of suicide
- overdiagnosis
- interventions being recommended for people who are not truly at high risk of AD/dementia (Gordon 2013; Calza et al. 2015, McKeever and Agius 2018; Weatherby and Agius 2018; Horstkötter et al. 2021; Schürmann and Trachsel 2023).

On the other hand, given the knowledge that we currently have about risk factors and preventative measures (Livingston et al. 2020), Horstkötter, Deckers and Köhler (2021) argue that it could be considered a moral fault *not* to apply upcoming insights (i.e. about prevention measures possibly but not solely resulting from population-based screening) that could potentially prevent harm by reducing the risk of AD/dementia in cognitively healthy middle-aged people.

With regard to the risk of recommending interventions to people who are not truly at high risk of AD/dementia (a point initially highlighted by Jungner et al. 1968), McKeever and Agius (2018) suggest that lifestyle modifications and existing treatments to lower cardiovascular risk factors are low risk and would therefore result in greater benefit than harm, since these factors are considered modifiable risk factors for dementia (as highlighted by Livingston et al. 2024). This argument widens the discussion about the risk-benefit ratio to include medication that is not specifically for the AD/dementia pathology but linked to cardiovascular health and risk.

Beneficence

Several potential benefits of screening (for cognitive frailty or risk of AD/dementia) have been highlighted (Gordon 2013; Calza et al. 2015; McKeever & Agius 2018; Horstkötter et al. 2021), namely,

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- Detection and correction of potentially reversible cognitive decline secondary to non-neurological disorders, malnutrition and inappropriate polytherapies.
- appropriate management of hospitalisation, surgery and anaesthesia
- appropriate safety measures to help prevent accidents
- better adherence and management of other medical conditions (linked to social isolation and depression)
- enabling policy makers to take decisions based on scientific evidence and to predict and plan care needs and housing decisions
- empowerment (knowledge of risk provides opportunity to take preventive measures)
- better planning for the future (e.g. wills, advance directives and real estate management)
- a feeling of some degree of control over a future “that may seem depressingly somber”
- reassurance (if low risk declared).

These potential benefits relate to society as well as to the individual.

- Empowerment or missed opportunities
- Autonomy and personal responsibility
- Blame and stigma
- Long-term impact of risk timeframe on personal life/identity

Empowerment or missed opportunities

The early awareness of risk and subsequent risk reduction methods of what is still considered as an incurable, neurodegenerative disease have been described as potentially leading to a sense of empowerment (McKeever & Agius 2018; Horstkötter et al. 2021). However, this is a fairly complex issue. The term “empowerment” is also a complex concept which can be approached from several perspectives and disciplines as diverse as ethics, public health, sociology and psychology, with slightly different meanings. For example, in the context of health care, empowerment often means actively involving citizens in their health journeys. In social psychology, it can also include a sense of self-efficacy or perceived control over one's life. Nonetheless, there are common attributes found in the literature such as i.) an enabling process, ii.) achieving personal change in relation to others and iii.) self-determination (Castro et al. 2016). “Empowerment” is generally seen as a positive outcome, giving people more control over their own health. In the context of risk prediction and awareness of risk, the reference to empowerment seems to be linked to the process of people acquiring freedom and power to do what they want or to control what happens to them in the light of that knowledge/awareness about risk.

Whilst it is often assumed that awareness of one's risk of AD/dementia might lead to lifestyle changes to improve health (e.g. for people identified as being at high risk) or reassurance (e.g. for people identified as being at low risk), there is no guarantee that people at high risk will be willing or able to make lifestyle changes (Bosco et al. 2020; Bruinsma et al. 2023) or that the “worried well” will actually be reassured (Gordon 2013). This has also been demonstrated in other conditions (e.g. Middleton, Anton & Perri 2013, Conway et al. 2016, and Deslippe et al. 2023) and challenges the portrayal of risk reduction programmes as a justification for population-based screening based on the principle of beneficence. On the other hand, there is also some evidence of lifestyle guidance at population level having a significant and positive effect on certain aspects of health (Li et al. 2022).

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Gordon (2013) points out that results of cognitive assessment tools indicating low risk does not necessarily provide reassurance, particularly to the worried well who might make lifestyle changes as precautionary measures without these changes necessarily meaning they stopped worrying. Consequently, it should not perhaps be assumed that lifestyle guidance linked to population level screening is always beneficial.

Autonomy and personal responsibility

The above-mentioned issue of whether people make lifestyle changes in response to information that they are at high risk of AD/dementia (or other conditions such as heart disease) is also linked to that of autonomy and to personal responsibility. In other words, if people are informed about their level of risk and about possible preventive measures, they have the opportunity to decide what, if anything, they would like to do about it and to bear in mind their level of risk when making decisions about various issues. Empowerment opens up the possibility of agency and hence responsibility for both negative and positive outcomes (Zinn (2020)). This may, in turn, contribute towards a shifting of the burden of prevention from the State onto the individual and to the attribution of blame and stigma.

Gordon (2013) questions whether knowing one’s risk is actually useful/beneficial to individuals or society, pointing out that statistics show that around 35% of people aged 80 will have some degree of cognitive impairment. Consequently, he suggests that people should perhaps all be encouraged to make those lifestyle changes and engage in advance planning, regardless of their estimated level of risk. So, whilst population screening may lead to greater awareness amongst parts of society that they are at high risk of developing AD/dementia, lifestyle changes and planning should not necessarily be limited to those people but rather recommended for everyone (Gordon 2013). Horstkötter et al. (2021) question whether early disclosure based on biomarker screening of cognitively healthy or slightly impaired people is ethically desirable as it might increase the likelihood of “individual responsabilisation”.

McKeever and Agius (2018) take an interesting approach to the issue by comparing a UK national vascular risk management programme (linking screening for risk with a risk reduction programme) with potential national screening (using the CAIDE Dementia Risk Score) for the risk of dementia, also linked to a cardiovascular risk reduction programme. The authors consider population-based screening for actual dementia as currently unethical but feel that screening for the *risk* of dementia involving minimal cost and minimal risk to patients would avoid “the ethical complexity associated with genetic testing” and not be in contradiction with Wilson and Junger’s criterion of there being “an accepted treatment for patients with accepted disease”. In comparison with cardiovascular disease for which there is some evidence of statins being helpful (but not currently for people at risk of dementia as a broad group), dementia risk would currently only benefit from lifestyle modifications which are classed as low risk interventions, if indeed people decide to take such measures. McKeever and Agius (2018) question whether informing patients of their risk of dementia is ethically justified but suggest that patients who are provided with reliable information about their risk of dementia, and about modifiable risk factors that are already routinely tested, and possible lifestyle changes, will be empowered to make important decisions linked to their risk of dementia.

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Blame and stigma

The relationship between perceived personal responsibility and blame/stigma was raised (Weatherby and Agius 2018; Horstkötter, Deckers and Köhler 2021; Schürmann and Trachsel 2023). It is suggested that a person who does not accept the offer to be tested for risk and subsequently develops the disease might be blamed (i.e. for not having taken appropriate measures to then reduce that risk or better plan for the probable condition), linking this to an increased likelihood of stigma and contributing to increased/unnecessary additional costs for society. The link between perceived responsibility for potentially discrediting shared attributes (based on the meanings that come to be attached to them) and a greater risk of stigma have been well described (e.g. by Jones et al. 1984; Weiner et al. 1988). In the context of population-based screening and risk reduction programmes for AD/dementia, it is also suggested that raising awareness about lifestyle changes that can be made by individuals to reduce risk may detract from what might otherwise be considered the obligations of social actors to strengthen educational and healthcare systems, and have safe public spaces. This shift to individual responsibility is reinforced by the healthy ageing paradigm (Schürmann and Trachsel 2023). This has economic implications as well as being linked to the negative impact that stigma may have on people’s lives.

Long-term impact of risk timeframe on personal life/identity

Gordon (2013) and Horstkötter, Deckers and Köhler (2021) draw attention to the potential impact of what is often an exceptionally long time between being identified as at risk and the actual occurrence of AD/dementia. Gordon asks whether being better at predicting the likelihood of developing dementia at some point is crucial to a person’s care plan (if indeed they even have one, bearing in mind this could involve screening cognitively healthy individuals). They consider the issue of potentially contradictory guidance for other health issues (e.g. taking measures to reduce the risk of one condition increasing the likelihood of another occurring) and of whether people would act on the advice provided over a prolonged period. The benefits and harms of encouraging younger people, in particular, to take measures to prevent a condition that *might* occur and if it does, probably many years or decades in the future, are questioned (Horstkötter et al. 2021).

Whilst not specifically focusing on population-level screening for dementia risk, McKeown, Mahli and Singh (2021) express concerns about the medicalisation of normal health, whereby large proportions of the population are labelled as being ‘at risk’. Horstkötter et al. (2021) suggest that it would be unethical to identify people at increased risk of developing a condition, entailing the loss of their identity as a healthy person, if there is nothing to offer them in terms of treatment or risk reduction strategies. They draw attention to the potential impact of a lengthy period of medicalised self-identity (i.e. as a person at risk of developing dementia), reflecting on how awareness of risk and efforts to reduce that risk might affect personal values (e.g. socialising being transformed from genuine care for friends into a risk reduction method, or certain dietary recommendations conflicting with people’s views about protection of the environment). The emotional and financial impact on people’s lives must also be considered (Gordon 2013).

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Issues at the level of society

Target condition for screening

Most articles focus on potential screening for the risk of developing AD or dementia. Calza et al. (2015), however, suggest that the target condition should be “cognitive frailty” which could cover cognitive impairment in neurological as well as non-neurological conditions. They consider the potential identification of non-neurological, treatable or reversible conditions as one of the two key goals of potential population-based screening, the other being the timely identification of people who are asymptomatic or in the early stage of a neurodegenerative disorder. Broadening the scope of such screening, the authors claim, should help identify the risk of non-neurological conditions that are still reversible, thus improving quality of life and disease outcome and preventing cognitive decline. This addresses the issue of beneficence in the sense that the potential benefit to the individual would be greater than if the only risk being assessed was for existing AD/dementia. In terms of potential benefits and risks, Calza et al. (2015) propose reframing the question about screening for risk as comparing the benefit of population-based cognitive screening (also covering non-neurological conditions) with the hazard of potential overdiagnosis of AD.

Validity and bias in the applicability of screening tools

It has been argued that screening tools should be “exquisitely sensitive, extremely specific and low-cost tools, to be administered on large populations of healthy people and resulting in a very accurate positive or negative predictive value, in order to monitor the so-called ‘detectable pre-clinical phase (DPCP)’”, which can be carried out anonymously or to identify people who are at risk, and is not a diagnostic procedure (cited in Calza et al. 2015, p.31). Calza et al. (2015) highlight the limited nature of certain screening tools for the risk of AD/dementia which only target specific disease mechanisms, as well as neuropsychological tests. They argue that whilst fairly effective as screening tools, they are often biased with regard to people with different educational levels, which is an example of inequity. The issue of bias and the possible use of screening tools that have not been validated on populations with a range of characteristics (e.g. educational, cultural and linguistic diversity) runs counter to the conduct of ethical research/clinical practice. According to Emanuel, Wendler and Grady (2000), for example, “value-enhancements of health or knowledge must be derived from the research” and for scientific validity, “the research must be methodologically rigorous”, which it is not if screening tools were not developed to ensure equal utility to people with different educational levels. Calza et al. (2015) call for more studies to compare the use of brief cognitive screening tests in the context of population-based screening versus more targeted approaches.

Whilst not explicitly stated, this reflects and has implications for health inequity because certain groups of people are either excluded from population-level screening or the results of such screening may not be accurate for them, resulting in some individuals being told they are at risk (when they are not) and vice versa.

Trade-off between accuracy and usefulness/relevance

A distinction can be made between screening for the benefit of society (e.g. anonymous screening for epidemiological, future planning, research, economic or policy making purposes) and screening for the benefit of the individual (Calza et al. 2015, Gordon 2013).

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Schürmann and Trachsel (2023) reflect on the trade-off between degree of accuracy, cost and burden of different screening approaches (e.g. of PET, CSF and blood-based biomarkers) combined with the lack of certainty as to whether someone will actually develop dementia. They acknowledge, however, that a combination of blood-based biomarkers may eventually come close to PET and CSF in terms of accuracy (Doroszkiewicz & Mroczko 2022). This raises concerns about how to communicate different types and levels of probable risk to people who are at risk.

Weatherby and Agius (2018) highlight the similarity between genetic testing for APOE ε4 allele and biomarkers for screening given they do not provide accurate information about whether and, equally important, when a person will develop dementia. They suggest that such screening approaches would merely indicate that people are at increased risk of developing dementia, with some potential implications for relatives and insurance eligibility, and may lead to discrimination in the workplace. This can be confusing and disturbing as people do not then know what to do. There should therefore be proper counselling and professional support before and after the test, where the broader implications for the family should be discussed. This is also relevant to discussions about the balance between risk and benefit, taking these issues beyond the individual. On the other hand, if greater accuracy and certainty were possible, the issue would no longer be about merely identifying risk but rather of predicting a timeframe for onset, which may be more useful to people but still a matter of probability.

Relationship to research

In this review, we excluded articles that were limited to the screening of individuals solely for the purpose of research because the ethical issues related to each are not necessarily the same and we wanted to avoid potential conflation of the two. A clear distinction must be made between population-based health screening and screening for the purpose of research with the latter being considered justifiable provided that the participants are well informed, including information that the research they are participating in will most likely not “bear fruit fast enough for them to benefit from it” (Weatherby and Agius 2018), (assuming that the results are beneficial and bearing in mind that research inherently includes risk of harm and is not designed to provide individual benefit). Consequently, widespread access to participation in research does not represent an alternative benefit that would compensate for the lack of existing treatment for people identified as being at high risk.

Economic considerations

Economic issues are also identified as ethical concerns, suggesting the need to explore the financial implications before dementia risk screening becomes standard practice, requiring the establishment of effective regulatory checks (Gordon 2013). Gordon comments on the financial interests of investors in the healthcare industry and the marketing of various screening tests which have the potential to reach huge audiences and are often described with great enthusiasm as major opportunities for healthcare practitioners and patients alike. Gordon also highlights caution voiced by Gauthier et al. in 2011 and 2012 linked to entering “the very lucrative diagnostic “preclinical” fray and surrounding the financial and ethical risks associated with the uncertainty of predictions, combined with the impact of receiving a “pre-disease” diagnosis on society and individuals”.

Another issue raised is whether it is ethical for doctors to receive financial incentives to provide such screening (Weatherby and Agius 2018) or for scarce public resources to be spent on screening and subsequent AD/dementia prevention programmes in the absence of solid, scientific evidence

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supporting the efficacy of such programmes, as opposed to those funds being spent elsewhere in the healthcare system for people with other medical conditions (Schürmann and Trachsel 2023). Horstkötter et al. (2021) nevertheless question whether waiting for such evidence and delaying implementation, in the light of the known social burden and avoidable individual harm associated with dementia, would actually be irresponsible.

Health inequity

Screening and prevention measures may be hampered by the existence and potential perpetuation of social injustice, whereby some groups of people are educationally or economically disadvantaged and thus unable to act on advice or benefit from measures in the context of secondary prevention resulting from health screening (Weatherby and Agius 2018; Schürmann and Trachsel 2023). These concerns focus on ethical principles such as beneficence, non-maleficence, respect for autonomy and justice, and highlight the debate about whether lifestyle changes (e.g. linked to diet and activity) are a sufficient justification for population-level screening (i.e. as some people will not be able to benefit from the alleged measures, either at all or to the same extent as other people). Horstkötter et al. 2021 summarise the complex relationship between empowerment, personal responsibility and equity as follows:

“Therefore, the upside of increased empowerment and control might be faced with the downside of an increased “individualized responsabilization” and the danger that some groups in society might turn out to be less able or less well positioned to pick up dementia risk reduction advice, further increasing existing health disparities” (Horstkötter et al. 2021, p.252).

4. LIMITATIONS

The exploration of reflection about ethical issues related to population-based screening for AD/dementia risk was a complex task. It required a search for details of ethical reflection about a practice that has yet to be implemented at population or large-scale group level in Europe but which has some things in common with assessment for the early detection of AD dementia or for other forms of dementia. Our aim was, however, to single out ethical reflection on the topic of AD/dementia population-level risk screening. This was further complicated by the lack of uniformity in the use of language around the topic of AD/dementia risk prediction. Whereas some authors speak about the *diagnosis* of MCI due to AD, others speak about it as the detection of a *risk* of AD dementia. Another issue is that of the terminology of pre-clinical AD as opposed to an asymptomatic/at-risk state along the continuum of the AD pathology. When reviewing older literature, it was especially important to be aware of references to AD being solely limited to AD dementia, reflecting a tendency to use the terms Alzheimer’s disease and dementia interchangeably.

The purpose and concept of diagnosis differs to that of screening and this is linked to the issue mentioned above. For example, one author may consider prodromal AD as representing a risk of AD dementia, another may consider it a pre-dementia stage and yet another may consider it a medical condition in its own right, albeit related to risk and/or to the near-certain development of AD dementia. Some authors referred to screening for dementia but also covered screening for the risk of developing dementia and it was therefore possible to include information about the latter, where the distinction between the two was clear.

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Another challenge was to distinguish between *ad hoc* testing and large-scale screening with authors often using the language of each in a way which led to some ambiguity. By limiting the review to health screening, it was relatively easy to reject literature on screening for inclusion in dementia research. However, as with the existence of ethical reflection on the broader issue of screening for dementia, excluding some ethical reflection related to screening for research meant not addressing some issues of potential relevance to population-level screening for risk. However, we feel that this was necessary as certain issues such as altruistic motives to contribute to research, the therapeutic misconception, the prior experience of some cognitive concerns in many cases and the limited/selected group targeted are important factors which may make it unhelpful for the purpose of seeing how the findings of this review relate to a possible future population-level screening and risk prevention project for AD dementia.

5. CONCLUSIONS

AD-RIDDLE is an exciting project which aims to connect risk prediction of Alzheimer’s disease to real-world preventive interventions by means of predictive algorithms, validated and accurate blood-based biomarkers and digital cognitive assessment tools. A further aim is to provide a decision toolkit to support healthcare professionals in matching patients with the right interventions. This scoping review has highlighted several relevant issues that would need to be considered in the future when developing or implementing the early detection/screening element of this work on a larger scale (e.g. at population level or for large sections of the general public). The review was also helpful in highlighting issues related to rapidly changing and overlapping concepts and terminology, which made the review challenging but also contributed towards a clearer definition of the issues or challenges that need to be addressed.

Some aspects to be considered within the AD-RIDDLE project:

- Long timeframe between identification of the risk and developing the disease
- Concerns of medicalisation of normal health in absence of treatment
- Disclosure of risk without certainty in the predictive values of the tests
- Validation in diverse populations
- Implications at the personal level (emotional and financial), interpersonal level (relatives) and potential effects in the workplace and insurance coverage.

In the very near future, as disease-modifying drugs gradually become available and part of the patient journey alongside preventive measures, some of the ethical issues and concerns raised may change and perhaps new issues will be raised. This is a fast-moving area and it is important to build on ethical reflection and adapt to changing realities, opportunities and threats. The recent approval of lecanemab by the European Medicines Agency, for example, as well as other disease modifying treatments on the horizon, has implications for discussions about the ethical implications of screening for the risk of Alzheimer’s disease/dementia. These developments may have implications at the level of public health and personal impact, with regard to costs, distribution of limited resources amongst different health conditions, validation of new treatments in diverse populations, further medicalisation of early AD, hope for patients but also the potential negative impact of reinforcing status as a person with a medical condition over a longer period of time, accompanied by potential risks and drawbacks to long-term drug treatment.

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The scoping review will feed into ongoing Public Involvement work with people who have cognitive problems, people with dementia, carers, older people and people considered at risk or with an interest in brain health to ensure that this research reflects their needs, concerns, hopes and priorities. In combination with the Public Involvement work and a policy and practice review, the review will inform the development of guidance and recommendations designed to inform the AD-RIDDLE platform design, feasibility testing and development, and promote further reflection on the socio-ethical implications of the project, all of which will facilitate the real-world implementation of the AD-RIDDLE project. It would therefore be premature to conclude this deliverable with concrete recommendations. At the same time, AD-RIDDLE is a dynamic project with decisions constantly being made which may affect the experience of research participants as well as future early detection and prevention programmes. We would therefore like to conclude with a few suggested questions for researchers to reflect on:

1. How can researchers communicate probabilistic risk disclosure in a personalised manner?
2. What training would clinicians/healthcare professionals need once early detection/screening are implemented?
3. What kind of explanatory materials and emotional and practical support might patients need?
4. How will researchers ensure and communicate to the public that screening tools have been properly validated on populations with different levels of education and cultural backgrounds?

We will further explore the ethical issues identified in this review and develop recommendations in the final deliverable/report D7.7 on ethical and societal guidance for AD-RIDDLE implementation which is due in Month 48 of the project.

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